

Practice abstract 03

Author: PoliRural consortium

Design: SPI

PoliRural Pilot Areas

PoliRural methodology is being tested in 12 regions across Europe plus Israel. The pilot selection was guided by a desire to include a wide spectrum of areas in relation to climate, geography, topography, social and economic conditions.

PoliRural pilot study areas are: **Flanders** (Belgium), **Monaghan** (Ireland), **Segóbriga** (Spain), **Vidzeme** (Latvia), **Mazowieckie** (Poland), **Central Bohemian Region** (Czech Republic), **Slovakia Region**, **Häme** (Finland), **Central Greece** (Greece), **Apulia** (Italy), **Gevgelija-Strumica** (Macedonia), and **Galilee** (Israel).

Policy makers, experts, farmers, rural dwellers and new entrants are main target groups in each pilot region defined as regional panel members. Each pilot has chosen the most appropriate approach to set up a regional panel and ensure efficient collaboration, certifying that the pilots' stakeholder engagement methodology is being followed.

Since the beginning of the project, PoliRural pilots have engaged 433 stakeholders. Of those, 107 are policy makers, 188 are members of the rural community, 68 representing rural newcomers, and 70 come from the research sector. Stakeholders have contributed to several tasks, namely to the production of pilot fiches, to the pan-European survey on rural needs, to the identification of drivers of change for rural areas and to the development of Statement of Purpose and Implementation Plan for each pilot.

Practice abstract 04

Author: PoliRural consortium

Design: SPI

The use of Text Mining in PoliRural

PoliRural combines survey research with innovative text mining techniques that are both rigorous and versatile. Text mining uses complex algorithms and cutting-edge technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning to detect patterns in vast amounts of text.

In PoliRural, text mining is extensively used at one of the foresight stages called current situation analysis. PoliRural's innovative approach enhances text mining results by blending them with those of Foresight and System Dynamic Modeling. This allows a more in-depth analysis to be undertaken in the 12 pilot areas, as the focus is not limited to the present but also covers possible future developments.

It should also be noticed that the use of text mining in PoliRural has some challenges, as follows:

- **Multilingual inputs:** The prototype solution was built around documents in English and in the later stages of the project will be adapted to regional contexts and languages, which is a challenging task, taking into consideration linguistic differences;
- **Semantic Discrepancies:** regardless of the results of model training, there will always be discrepancies in the human understanding of certain concepts and a machine estimation of those concepts;
- **Monitoring and maintenance:** the creation of the text mining solution for PoliRural is an iterative process not only in terms of its development, but also its usage. The solution will need constant monitoring and maintenance.

Practice abstract 05

Author: PoliRural consortium

Design: SPI

The concept of Rural Attractiveness in PoliRural

PoliRural has a simple, if ambitious, objective - to make rural places and professions more attractive for established rural populations and recent or potential newcomers. In order to clarify the rural attractiveness's vision, the following research activities were performed: comparison of pilot regions according to their development indicators; comparison of survey results not only by region but also by responses of different question groups; SWOT analysis in pilot regions; needs-policy mapping and regional needs prioritization exercises.

Some conclusions have resulted from this analysis. Our regions view rural development through the prism of rural attractiveness, which varies from pilot to pilot. Some view rural attractiveness from the point of view of people who already live there, with the intention of reversing population decline. Some want to make rural professions more attractive, by focusing on jobs other than farming. Some envision attractive rural regions as a place suitable for living and home-working, while others emphasise the need to focus on entrepreneurs coming from abroad.

At the beginning, PoliRural developed a universal definition of rural attractiveness: "Rural attractiveness encompasses sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment. There is an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced".

But as the project develops, it may be far more productive to encourage regions to develop their own unique concept or concepts of rural attractiveness. One that is based on their own needs, aligned with their own values, sense of identity and vision of the future.

Practice abstract 06

Author: PoliRural consortium

Design: SPI

The use of System Dynamics in PoliRural

System Dynamics is a modelling technique that helps to understand the dynamic behavior of complex systems. PoliRural faces the challenge to test and demonstrate the potential usefulness of System Dynamics modelling and facilitate its access to rural communities and policy makers.

During the first year of PoliRural project, a template model of System Dynamics has been built, as well as some sample models to understand the usefulness of modelling exercise. The template model deals with Rural Attractiveness, a central issue in PoliRural, defined by different factors (e.g., natural capital, social capital, employment, quality of life). Each of these factors has a weight in the decision to move to or stay in a rural area, and it can be regulated in the interface. The template model is being adapted and calibrated for every pilot area.

Some lessons learned during the creation of these models are the following:

- Due to the inherent complexity of a model, it is challenging to make it useful and relevant. In particular, it is not easy to reflect local dynamics and keep the model simple and understandable by non-experts;
- Moreover, it has proven to be difficult to combine the complexity of the model and a user-friendly interface in any SDM software environment.

Over the next few months, PoliRural will try to address these issues, with a view to creating a System Dynamics solution that has a strong explanatory and sustainability potential.

